

Easy Steps To Learn Astrology Online?

A Complete Learning Guide

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Want to **Learn Astrology Online**? You can learn astrology online by reading this guide, here I have provided all the resources that you will ever require to learn about astrology online

What is Astrology?

The fundamental dimensions of existence are time and space. Being in the wrong place at the wrong time, or in the right place at the wrong time, causes us to miss out on opportunities in life, no matter how valuable they may be so & you feel like there is something mysterious about them, something you cannot explain.

So, how about getting to the bottom of how astrology works? Astrology has been around for centuries, and it has been used to chart paths, predict events, and unlock the

mysteries of the universe.

Why learning Astrology is important?

Astrology is a practice that has been around for thousands of years. It is based on the system that the positions of the planets and stars have an effect on human lives. From ancient times, astrologers have used the stars and planets to make predictions about the future and to gain insight into human behaviour.

Astrologer has to be very precise when it comes to predicting events that will happen again and again in life & the native depends on it. The more accuracy, the better it is for the client to come and trust future events. This science requires years of experience to gain a deeper understanding of the subject applying science for the benefit of people.

How To Learn Astrology online ?

Learning Astrology online is difficult as there are many sources to find as the field of astrology is very wide and much needed to explore.

So here on this page you will find all the sources which you ever needed to learn astrology from the very basic to the advance level, here i have mention all the sources in step wise format so i recommend you to read this full page to acquire all the knowledge about astrology.

Lesson: Basic of Astrology

The aim of this lesson is to introduce astrology for beginners and help them to understand the important and basics aspects of astrology. Here we have made five separate Chapters in steps wise format on the basics of astrology and discuss all the important aspects of astrology

Chapter 1: The Zodiac Sign

Chapter 2: Planets and houses

Chapter 3: The Nakshatras

Chapter 4: The Dasha System

Chapter 5: Interpreting the Charts

Find free resources for learning astrology online?

The following is a list of free resources you can use if you wish to learn astrology online. After you have studied the resources, you will be equipped with a great deal of knowledge. These sources will help you to learn astrology for free without compromising on quality

FREE ASTROLOGY COURSE

LEARN ASTROLOGY WITH FREE WEBINAR

FREE ACCESS TO ASTROLOGY DATA BANK

GET ACCESS TO FREE ASTROLOGY VIDEOS

FREE ASTROLOGY CALCULATORS

FREE ASTROLOGY E- BOOKS

ASK FREE QUESTIONS TO ASTROLOGERS

GET DAILY - MONTHLY FREE PREDICTIONS

[View Free Astrology Sources](#)

**All Astrology Books written and recommended
by Deepanshu Giri ji**

“

I have over 1200 books in which some of them are manuscripts, some handwritten and I haven't come across a book that hasn't taught me anything as sometimes it's not the time that you will get the essence of the book, As if you are mentally prepared the book will start revealing everything you need to know and beyond it and even a single sentence will start giving you cramps due to happiness and the same book will seem ordinary for some other person.

Deepanshu Giri ji

Books written by Deepanshu Ji

Books recommended by Deepanshu ji

It is now time for the next step

After reviewing the above free astrology sources, I hope that you will be armed with comprehensive knowledge of astrology and ready to advance astrology courses if you wish to become an expert in all fields of astrology.

These Levels consist of the Following Courses

Level 1 : Courses

Foundation course in Astrology

Level 2 : Courses

Predictive Astrology Course Part -1

Predictive Astrology Course Part -2

Level 3 : Courses

A course on Navansha – Jamini Sutra

Kaal Chakra Dasha Course

Yogini Dasha Course

Level 4 : Courses

Karma and Relationship Course

Badhak Level 1 Astrology Course

Badhak Level 2 Astrology Course

Level 5 : Courses

Predictive Nakshatra Course

Additional Courses

Lal Kitab Course

One Course to learn Complete Astrology

We have combined First 4 levels and make it into single course so it will become easy for those who are looking for single and complete astrology course. This Astrology course is going to cover all aspects of astrology and also suitable for those who are looking for Diploma or Certification Course.

ASTROLOGY COURSE

DURATION : 2 YEARS

- ✔ Basic to expert level learning
- ✔ Covers all aspects of astrology
- ✔ Pre-recorded lessons
- ✔ Live doubt sessions
- ✔ Updated lessons
- ✔ Astrologer Consultation
- ✔ Certificate Of Completion

- By Deepanshu Giri

2 -Year Diploma Course

After completing this comprehensive Astrology Course, you will become an expert in all fields of Astrology and a professional Jyotish analyst

- Basic to Expert Level Learning
- Covers all Aspects of Astrology
- Pre recorded Videos
- Doubt Session Classes
- Latest Books and Magazine
- Astrologer consultation
- Professional Certification

[Learn about Diploma course in Detail](#)

“Now its upto you, You can choose a complete 2 year Course or Choose courses in level wise or even you can choose a single course as well”

The Following Table summaries the Fees for all of our Astrology Courses

Online Astrology Courses Links	Teacher Name	Fees
2 Year Certificate Course in Vedic Astrology	Deepanshu Giri	137,900/-
The Astrology Foundation Course	Deepanshu Giri	23,900/-
Predictive Astrology Part - 1 (Hindi+English)	Deepanshu Giri	34,400/-
Predictive Astrology Part - 2 (Hindi+English)	Deepanshu Giri	31,000/-
Predictive Astrology Part - 2 (Hindi)	Deepanshu Giri	25,000/-
Learn Predictive Astrology Part - 2 (English)	Deepanshu Giri	25,000/-

Online Astrology Courses Links	Teacher Name	Fees
Yogini Dasha Astrology Course	Deepanshu Giri	15,000/-
Badhak Planets and Remedies astrology course	Deepanshu Giri	Free Course
Predictive Nakshatra Astrology Course	Deepanshu Giri	25,060/-
Jamini Sutram Level 1 Astrology Course	Deepanshu Giri	11,500/-
Kaal Chakra Dasha Astrology Course	Deepanshu Giri	7000/-
Lal Kitab Astrology Course	Deepanshu Giri	29,500/-
Karma and Relationships Astrology Course	Deepanshu Giri	9,500/-
Learn Lunar Astro Webinars	Deepanshu Giri	1,770/-

LATEST ASTROLOGY SOFTWARES (JYOTISH SOFTWARE)

The top professional ASTROLOGY SOFTWARE are –

1. Bhrigu Software
2. Red Astro Premium 8.0
3. Red Astro Professional 8.0
4. Astro Data Bank – free online astrology software.

With the help of these Jyotish Software, you can make predictions, match Kundli, suggest remedies, analyse Varshaphal and many more. All of these horoscope software are incredibly accurate. Read the descriptions below for all the software to know the best suitable astrology software for yourself.

Astrology Software	Price	Level	Compatibility
Astro Data Bank Software	Free / Lifetime	Beginners & Experienced	Windows / Mobile
Bhrighu Software	17,700 / Lifetime	Beginners & Experienced	Windows
Red Astro Premium Software	17,700 / Lifetime	Experienced	Windows
Red Astro Professional Software	8,500 / Lifetime	Experienced	Windows

Now Why To Choose Lunar Astro?

From Fundamental Astrology to Stunning Blank Chart Predictions

Lunar Astro is famous as students start predicting here from day one. All Online Astrology Courses at Lunar Astro are designed in such a way that you can start doing predictions even from the first lecture of Predictive Astrology Part – 1. We have also launched The Foundation Course – Essential of Astrology for those who have zero knowledge about astrology but have a great interest in learning astrology.

If you have decided to pursue astrology online and do stunning predictions, then Lunar Astro courses are there for you. We always inspire our students in our classes that the students to learn in such a deep way to predict on a blank chart. Using only the energy of the signs you should be able to predict at least 40-45 events later on when you put planets in it.

Now lets Take a Quick overview about all the above courses for more understanding

Level - 1

Foundation Course in Astrology

This is the fundamental course for learning astrology, this is one of the most selling course of ours as it covers the fundamental of astrology in great details.

If You are new to astrology and have no idea about how to start and which course to take then this course is recommended for you.

Click the Link below to see in details

[learn more about foundation course](#)

Level - 2

ABOUT PREDICTIVE ASTROLOGY COURSE PART – 1

In this premium astrology course, all lectures will be available as recorded sessions but you will get a chance to go through live doubt sessions every month. This Online Jyotish Course comes with 37 Lessons [18 lectures + 12+ recorded QA sessions to clear doubts.

Total 90+ hours of lecture only on 12 signs and 9 planets have been delivered in this Online Jyotish Learning Course. You can Learn Astrology as detailed as it can get.

You will get Jaimini Sutram level – 1 [ATMAKARKA] Astrology Course free of cost worth Rs. 11000 with the PREDICTIVE ASTROLOGY PART – 1

The Predictive **Astrology Course** has been designed in a very creative and simple way that even if you are an absolute beginner and want to start your journey in Jyotish, this **Online Astrology Course** is for you and if you are a practicing astrologer with few years of experience and lacking behind somewhere in the field of studying Jyotish via online

mediums, so with Lunar Astro quality content, you can study Jyotish via zoom and boost your techniques and skills to an advance level.

This **Basic Astrology Course** consists of many question and answer sessions solving your doubts in **Astrology Classes**. You will learn solutions over your astrology practices from very basics to advanced level. All the accessible astrology courses are provided in both languages in English and Hindi. So that one can easily understand the astrology course and study jyotish online in a better manner. Kindly see the **curriculum section** to see all lectures by name.

[Click here to view Curriculum](#)

[Enroll For Prediction Astrology part -1](#)

ABOUT PREDICTIVE ASTROLOGY COURSE PART – 2

This is a revised Predictive Astrology Course with new techniques and content to learn astrology [online] and take astrology to an advanced level. This online jyotish course will make you experience true astrology and its value.

In the new version of the **ONLINE PREDICTIVE ASTROLOGY COURSES**, you will Study Astrology (Jyotish) with new techniques and you will study how to make predictions from Planets in Houses and things that are more enhanced in terms of predictive capabilities. This **Online Jyotish Course** will be more practical, easy to grasp and implement and help you in further learning astrology in a more simplified manner for beginners as well as practicing astrologers.

This Astrology Course will consist 2 lectures on a single topic from two different batches and the detailed part is as below:

- Planets in houses and their predictions along with special positions when they occupy and how special events get manifested in life.
- How to remain happy and sort out all your problems using the qualities of Rashis

[Zodiac] so that you can motivate yourself, predict and provide remedies and acquire knowledge and implement astrology knowledge for Happiness.

-Nature-based remedies and planetary-based remedies.

-Blank Chart Predictions while learning astrology online within online astrology courses.

-Dasa Systems which was never revealed before anywhere includes House Code, Zodiac Code, and Planetary Code.

What do these online astrology courses teach you in terms of value – You will realise the amount of content delivered is something on which you can not put the price.

Remedies related to 12 signs in our online astrology courses.

[Enroll For Prediction Astrology part -2](#)

Level - 3

Kaal Chakra Dasha – Astrology Course in Hindi & English

To acquire knowledge of astrology via zoom and master it, it is important to learn this astrology course in a very serious manner. This astrology course will help you in predicting all the major and minor events of life as over a period of time I have used this dasha along with other dasha to predict various events The content session is of a 4-hour duration in which I have covered all the technical aspects, keywords for rashis, and implementation using quantum jumps to time the events. Things you will learn in this online astrology course:

- Good and Bad Periods of life
- Timing of health-related issues using Transits with respect to this dasha
- Timing of Marriage
- Timing of Job

[Learn More about Kaal Chakra Dasha Course](#)

Yogini Dasha Astrology Course – Timing of Job and Marriage – Hindi | English

In this online astrology course, you are going to learn in astrology that how to time events using the Asht-Yogini's along with the divisional charts. And, most importantly a very big secret is going to be revealed in terms of the sequencing of the dasha used till now which is very much different from what is being taught in classics and books. As this system has been tested on several charts and major aspects for each planet along with remedies has been discussed during the course like planets 8th to Rahu changes their behaviour suddenly so if Venus is 8th to it – **native's relationships and financial position change rapidly.**

This online Jyotish course includes:

- Dasa systems and their applications
- Timing of Job, Demotion, Promotion, Gains, Change of Job, etc
- Timing of Marriage, Divorce, Troubles, etc
- Story of Asht Yogini's and their implementation in dasa system
- Divisional charts like D9 (for marriage)
- Ups and Downs in Profession using D10
- Best Period as well as Bad Periods determination in life
- Special positions of planets like combustion, debilitation, retrogression, digbala, mulatrikona, etc; – their workings and implementation on the dasa system
- Remedies and how to make those based on different charts.

[Learn More about Yogini Dasha Astrology Course](#)

Karma and Relationships (Match-Making) Online Astrology [Course]

In the ASTROLOGY course of Karma & Relationship of Lunar Astro, Deepanshu Giri has taught the advanced system of Marriage matchmaking as per the pending karma of both the native. As most astrologers use the 36 Gunas system for matchmaking which is not relevant in today's world. You will see marriage with 30 points fails and on the other hand marriage with only 17 points goes well.

That is why you need to study JYOTISH ONLINE to learn the advanced systems and new techniques on marriage match-making to predict everything exactly about the married life of the native. In this course on Marriage Astrology, Deepanshu Giri has

taught how to match the charts, how to predict the timing of Marriage, Remedies to be performed for good married life, and the pending karma associated with the spouse.

This Jyotish Course on Marriage Includes

- Pending Karma with respect to Relationships and Marriage and Quality of Married Life
- Timing of Marriage and Nature of Spouse, From Where Spouse will come
- Match Making and Compatibility of Marriage
- Cause of Suffering in Married Life and Remedies for Marriage

[Learn More about Karma & Relationships Course](#)

Level - 4

Badhak Planet and Remedies – Online Astrological Course

When it comes to learning astrology online from the best, Lunar Astro Badhak Planets and Remedies, online astrological courses. In this astrology course, Deepanshu Giri Ji will teach you the astrology basics of the Badhak Planets both for Hindi and English learners. This online Jyotish course mainly covers:

What are Badhak Planets and their remedies? and How do Badhak Planets work?
How to find your Badhak Planet & How to use them? Badhak Astrology Course Validity – 1 Year

Badhak Online Astrology Course Language – English Course Type – Recorded. [Live Question Ans Sessions Included]

[Learn More about Badhak Planet and Remedies](#)

Level - 5

Learn Predictive Nakshatra – Astrology Course

This astrology course is designed in a way such that any nakshatra irrespective of the planet occupying it or not will give results and how to make predictions will be taught in this course because this astrology course is derived from a very rare classic called Rohini Tara Samhita written by Nathu Lal Goswami Maharaj. This astrology course will also teach you about the activation ages of nakshatra and how the events get manifested in your own life and the mythology associated with each of these nakshatras will be discussed in detail.

I will also cover the pending karma associated with each nakshatra and lineage issues and how the curse manifests in your chart and identify the life pattern. And, bonus techniques, as well as tithi-based techniques too, are included in this course along with the base correction required for the chart to initialize the readings. This online astrology course contains :

Curse and boons are associated with each nakshatra and their manifestation along with identification based on your life patterns. Things you will be going to focus on in these Jyotish courses:

- Pending Karma decoding of a chart from Karam Vipak Samhita.
- Timing of activation of each nakshatra.
- Base Correction and other aspects of the nakshatra.

[Learn More about Predictive Nakshatra Course](#)

Lal-Kitab – Astrology Course

When it comes to learning astrology, Lal-Kitab is one of the strongest parts of astrology. This Jyotish course of Lunar Astro Jyotish course is taught by Najoomi Ji who will help in making you understand how Lal Kitab works and many aspects of it which are not been covered anywhere before. Also, being an uncategorised book which means there is no structured lesson plan so all topics which were confusing to you like the usage of Grahfal (results of the planet) or the Rashifal (the result of the signs) will be made clear

along with the remedies and corrections and logic behind those. This online astrological course mainly covers:

- Planets and their explanation with respect to Lal Kitab and How to read and decode Lal Kitab
- Graham, Rashifal, and their major differences and Matsui or artificial planets and their usage
- Planets that are sleeping and their essence, 35-year dasha cycle and 12 houses and their description as per Lal Kitab and Badshah and Wazir planets.
- When will planets when activated give their results? and Lal Kitab remedies

Course Language: Hindi Only and Course Instructor: Najoomi Ji (Daljeet Singh)

[Learn More about Lal-Kitab course](#)

Astrology Blogs

Reading quality blogs regularly will not only keep you updated but also it will help you to uncover the new and hidden topics which you may not get by reading any books or courses.

It is the author Deepanshu Giri Ji who is the best part of this section.

Science of Rahu Kaal

We all have heard this term from our elders to not perform anything during the Rahu kaal as every day for 90 minutes there is

[READ MORE »](#)

20 August 2023 • 61 Comments

Bhrigu's and Saturn

In our chart, there are possibilities of several hundred yogas present applicable, and as an astrologer, it is pretty challenging to remember more than 30-40

READ MORE »

8 August 2023 • 65 Comments

Remedies of DNA

We all get developed as per our DNA structure, but based on our food habits, our DNA gets energised. Such as eating spices- Places where

READ MORE »

3 August 2023 • 84 Comments

Jupiter – Your Sweet 16

Pay by Happiness- Every planet has its commodity, and this commodity is allocated based on the quality of the planet. Such as Moon is emotion,

[READ MORE »](#)

27 July 2023 • 63 Comments

Rain of Peace- A ritual of Rain

Indra- The god of Thunder and Rains and he is the one responsible for all the wealth, comfort and peace in life he blesses humans

READ MORE »

19 July 2023 • 2 Comments

Ketu – Seven Stages of Liberation

Today on Shanivaar, Shasti Tithi- when you feel bondage, Let me try to give you relief by talking about Moksh karaka- Ketu. The energy of

READ MORE »

24 June 2023 • 43 Comments

Frequently Asked Questions

1. What is Vedic Astrology?

Vedic astrology, also known as Jyotish, is a traditional form of astrology that originated in ancient India. It is based on the Vedic texts, which date back to 3000 BCE, and it uses the position of the stars and the lunar mansions to make predictions and analyze a person's personality and potential.

2. What are the main components of Vedic Astrology Charts?

A Vedic astrological chart, also known as a Janam Kundli, includes the positions of the planets in the zodiac signs, the lunar mansion, and the positions of the ascendant and the Moon.

Astrologers use this chart to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the planets and make predictions about a person's life.

3. What is a Birth chart and how it is used in Astrology ?

In a birth chart, also known as a natal chart, the sky is mapped at the exact time and place of a person's birth. A person's potential and personality can be analyzed and predicted using this chart by an astrologer.

4. How much Time it will take to Learn Astrology?

If you have dedication, seriousness, good grasping power and do practice while learning astrology one can easily complete the course in 3 months. But we do not promise to make you an astrologer within a few days, because it is a slow process but the content you will get from us will help you in becoming an expert astrologer.

5. I have a busy schedule, can I make time to learn astrology?

Yes, with us this is the biggest advantage, that you can study from home or anywhere in the world. We are open to all. As we have recorded lessons you can access them anytime and learn astrology anytime. What if my payment gets failed during Astrology Courses registration?

In such case please contact astrolunar108@gmail.com our amazing support team will revert you back in working hours!

6. How to Enroll in any Online Astrology Course to start learning the astrology online?

Lunar Astro's learn astrology online program has provided you with a complete DIY learning system to guide you how to learn astrology. This system will Enroll you in any ASTROLOGY COURSE ONLINE.

What you have to do is just to click on the ENROLL NOW button below any astrology course page. Once you will be on a course page it will reflect an ADD TO CART button above the

course. Click on ADD TO CART. It will redirect you to a form where you can fill in your information and proceed to the payment page. You can make payments using several payment methods. As soon as the payment is processed the course will be enrolled into your profile. Which you can access by clicking on MY COURSE from the top of MENU or Home Page.

7. Which Astrology Course should I take first to start learning astrology from the basics?

To learn astrology from online sources and basics, you can start learning PREDICTIVE ASTROLOGY PART-1 and PREDICTIVE ASTROLOGY PART-2. The benefits of starting from basics:

Even if you do not know anything about astrology but want to pursue an astrology course, this course will help you in learning the basics of astrology.

1. You will be able to start prediction. From the very first course.
2. Acquire knowledge about planets and rashis with all remedies.
3. Blank chart predictions.
4. Dasha systems include house code, zodiac code, and planetary code.

8. Ideally How much time it will take to Learn Astrology ?

If you have dedication, seriousness, good grasping power and do practice while learning astrology one can easily complete the course in 3 months. But we do not promise to make you an astrologer within a few days, because it is a slow process but the content you will get from us will help you in becoming an expert astrologer.

9. What is the best astrology software to become a Professional Astrologer?

To become a professional astrologer one should master ASTROLOGY SOFTWARE too. Lunar Astro is offering the best 5 astrology software while learning astrology online with lunar astro online astrology courses, with the best price, these 5 astrology softwares will help you with the basic skills to advance.

Here is the astrology software offered by Lunar Astro:

1. Astro Data Bank
2. Bhrihu Software
3. Red Astro Premium
4. Red Astro Professional
5. Parashara Light

10. What are the best books to learn astrology?

In Deepanshu sir's lectures, he recommended many [astrology books](#) that are very useful while you are learning astrology with Lunar Astro Vedic Academy.

11. Can I learn astrology online for free?

Yes you can learn Astrology online Lunar Astro is providing an [online astrology free course](#), you can visit Lunar Astro.

12. What type of study material would be there in Online Astrology Courses?

We will provide you with various PPTs and Compilations (of various assignments and texts) so that you can practice and master this journey of learning astrology. We do not send printed material or books to you however during the courses. There are several books suggested which are worth and rare to read that have been suggested & in Pre – reads tab after you have enrolled for the course.

13. Who is the best astrologer on YouTube?

The best astrologer in India is Deepanshu Giri ji, he has more than 330 free astrology videos on his YouTube channel LunarAstro, which you should check out if you wish to learn astrology online.

14. Is it possible to learn astrology for free?

It seems that learning Astrology in free is impossible, as there is so much in Astrology to comprehend that it is difficult to find it. However, if all the sources are available in one place and are explained in a step-by-step manner in video format, then I believe it will be easy to understand. The Lunar Astro YouTube channel is the only platform that offers 350+ astrological videos for free, which are made by Deepanshu Gir Ji himself, a renowned astrologer.

For More you can visit wiki how page – [3 ways to Learn Astrology](#).

15. Why choose Lunar Astro to study Astrology Online?